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MOVEMENT OF PRICES, UNEMPLOYMENT RATE AND THE ROMA CONTENT IN THE DAILIES, AUGUST 2010 – FEBRUARY 2011

Lubomir Stoytchev¹

Abstract

In this article, I have explored the effect of two macroeconomic processes on the volume of Roma content in six Bulgarian daily newspapers. Using Eurostat macroeconomic data and press monitoring results produced by an independent nonprofit, I test for the presence of a significant association between the volume of content of Roma related articles and the movement of prices – in particular, the food and non-alcoholic product prices, and the diesel and unleaded 95 fuel prices. Further, the association between the unemployment rate and the volume of content of Roma related articles is tested. Interesting results show that the overall movement of prices is not significantly correlated with the volume of Roma content in the dailies. On the other hand, the unemployment rate and the price of diesel and food products appear to be in a strong and significant association with the volume of Roma content. A similar type of association though cannot be proved when it comes to a nationalistic daily.

Key words: inflation indicators, diesel price, petrol price, unemployment, Roma content, daily newspapers.

INTRODUCTION

A great deal of changes and social processes, including such as stratification, socialisation, institutionalisation, mobility, digitalisation, depopulation, pauperisation, ethnicisation, etc., have been taking place in present-day Bulgarian society. Beside the *societal* in the above and the like processes, I render an account of an increasing number of other aspects: environmental, economic, geographic, media, technological, etc. Exactly the increased multifaceted and intertwining nature of the contemporary *societal* makes it difficult to research, understand and mostly to model and forecast. I would really like this very situation to become the **contextual reading environment** for everyone interested in this study (and in every other paper in the field of social science).

The interaction between technology and the *societal* has already demonstrated its potential to generate and develop unprecedented in world history phenomena. For less than a year, the world has witnessed how Twitter played a key role during the collapse of the political regime in Egypt (Bergstrom; 2011). Twitter can be referred to as an applied product of elements from the social network theory (sociology) and the network theory (informatics/computer science). The situation is not very different

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when social processes intertwine with climatic, environmental and other processes. It is not only that new terms appear (firstly, in professional jargons and then) in people's vocabulary but also unseen before phenomena.

The steadily complicating social structure and the development of new ways for communication further enrich the diversity and multiformity of social processes. If ways of communication are accepted as the means used by participants to share information (e.g. via face to face communication, through paper /an electronic device or over the Internet), I would like to explicitly specify one of the many essential aspects concerning the exchange of content: its **velocity**. And despite the great importance of the velocity (or the choice of communication velocity) issues, the focus of this study is different: **to what extent certain economic processes influence the content in the Bulgarian dailies as one of the primary sources of information in present-day society**. Setting aside (but always keeping in mind) most important questions concerning communication and media, e.g. velocity, accuracy, etc. of the exchange of content, I decided to put effort in studying the association between some macroeconomic processes and the Roma media content.

METHODOLOGICAL NOTES

This paper is an attempt for analysis of associations between selected economic processes and the volume of Roma ethnic content in two types of media: newspapers published on daily basis (dailies) and electronic newspapers (info portals) which update the content they publish every day. For methodological reasons other types of media, such as weeklies and monthlies, blogs, etc., were not monitored. Without going into detail here, I argue that it is important all media included in comparative studies should be as identical as possible in terms of the velocity at which they update/exchange the content they publish.

For seven months (from August 2010 to February 2011), a team of young members from non-government organisations have monitored six national daily newspapers. The sources of information were monitored for various purposes, among which was an analysis of content of articles related to particular Roma persons or the Roma community. In this study, though, I used only recorded data presenting the monthly number of Roma related articles in the monitored media. Furthermore, the analysis required the use of indicators of inflation and employment; in this respect, I used inflation rates, employment rates and prices data from Eurostat and the European Energy Portal.

The collected data was processed and analysed through statistical methods: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (called Pearson's correlation for short) and Box-Pierce portmanteau test for autocorrelation. Calculations were made through the statistical package Stata, version 9.2.

ECONOMIC PROCESSES AND THEMATIC CONTENT IN THE MEDIA

It is hard to imagine that the critically reading public has never asked itself how come that in so many specific situations media tend to pay attention

to particular topics and avoid others. There are no simple answers to that question but through sound reasoning one can get to different explanations such as: prejudiced judgments of editorial boards should have something to do with the content of the breaking news and articles; the financial situation of media usually restricts expenses and allows journalists and reporters to cover very few topics and events which take place within the narrow boundaries of a territory; alternative sources of funding (different from sales, advertising, sponsors, etc.) may have influence on the selection of topics that should be covered and so forth.

The rest of the public, who avoid thinking about the above issues, most probably prefers to accept that media content is what actually takes place. Taking on trust this socially constructed world by media, the public (in most cases) tries to modify their behaviour according to what is being disseminated. And this should have something to do with the fundamental mechanisms of control of the alleged fourth branch of power.

Of course, the critically reading public can also fall into this mechanism. Being permanently bombarded with burning questions of the day (carefully selected and disseminated by media), even critical readers (quite often) find themselves trapped within the constructed reality of the media world. This is how media content becomes the content of thinking of large social groups.

Without denying the above-mentioned, I argue that there are processes which (to a certain extent) influence the content management decisions made by editorial boards; these processes do not take place on individual level. What I have in mind are topics which cannot be avoided or distorted; in case these topics are avoided or distorted, it is highly probable that (in a relatively free market environment) the financial results of such media will plummet (for example, loss of market share and respectively reduced revenues). Certainly, these topics are the **economic issues** and the **burning questions** of the day; some of which are the Roma problems.

Issues concerning ethnicity and some macroeconomic processes represent the focus of this study. Within so many economic issues there are some which cannot (should not) be avoided by the leading daily newspapers. Paying special attention to food product and fuel prices, all of us observe directly or indirectly the movement of prices process (on daily basis). A very small percentage of the population is not interested in increase or decrease in prices of goods. The same can be argued about employment issues: the possibility a person to lose his/her job and the probability to get new and better-paid one depend not only on the profile of the individual but also on the labour market situation.

Ethnicity problems and the Roma issue, in particular, provoke great interest; articles about Roma can be found in every edition of the dailies under discussion. We can only presume the reasons for such an interest; in addition to the centuries-long tradition of Roma and Bulgarians living together on the Balkans, there is one remarkable peculiarity – the *differences*, e.g. way of living, conception of the world, needs and priorities, language, intonation, skin colour, etc. And *differences* are always a topic that provokes interest (and sells) – in some cases as a threat or exoticness, and in others as an alternative to something, etc.

The idea about an existing association between the economic processes which people face every single day when they go shopping (incl. at the petrol station), work or plan how to spend their free time and the topics in the media originated within

the context of the above thoughts. That became the **major research question** in this study: **is there a relationship between some macroeconomic processes (e.g. inflation and unemployment) and the volume of the Roma thematic content in the media?**

The hypotheses tested in this study were defined on the basis of content from six monitored media, e.g. the newspapers *Ataka*, *Novinar*, *Monitor*, *Dnevnik*, *Klassa* and the news portal *Dnes.bg*. With regard to definitions of hypotheses, the following approach was applied: hypotheses were constructed and tested not only for all the monitored media but also for specific type of media. The *Ataka* newspaper allowed me to test hypotheses within a context of a nationalistic medium. The rest of the sources provided an environment to test how hypotheses worked within the framework of non-nationalistic (liberal) media. The ideological discourse of a medium was defined using a *nationalistic – non-nationalistic* binary variable. Articles (content) were classified according to values they stood up for. Respectively, the type of a daily was defined according to vindicated values using the *nationalistic – non-nationalistic* variable.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The number of hypotheses seems considerably large for a blitz study like this one. As a matter of fact, a closer scrutiny reveals that several basic hypotheses can be outlined; the rest of hypotheses only redefine the basic ones and their sole purpose is to test some informative and interesting aspects which are not clearly explained only through the basic hypotheses testing.

Movement of prices hypotheses

1. Do the **overall changes of prices** and the **changes of prices of food products and non-alcoholic beverages, petrol and diesel** lead to **changes in the number of Roma articles**, published in the monitored media?
2. Do the **changes of prices of food products and non-alcoholic beverages, petrol and diesel** lead to **changes in the number of Roma articles**, published in media having *non-nationalistic* editorial policy?
3. Do the **changes of prices of food products and non-alcoholic beverages, petrol and diesel** lead to **changes in the number of Roma articles**, published in media having *nationalistic* editorial policy?

Unemployment hypotheses

1. Do the **changes of the unemployment rate** lead to changes in the **number of Roma articles**, published in the monitored media?
2. Do the **changes of the unemployment rate** lead to changes in the **number of Roma articles**, published in media having *non-nationalistic (liberal)* editorial policy?
3. Do the **changes of the unemployment rate** lead to changes in the **number of Roma articles**, published in media having *nationalistic* editorial policy?

Sources of information and variables

The major sources of information in this study are three, all of which I consider reliable and correct. The data sources and the variables (including their acronyms) generated from these data are listed in the tables below; the generated variables were used in the statistical analysis.

Variable	Variable details	Definition of variable
Harmonised index of consumer prices - HICP	HICP is measured on monthly basis. Base – 2005 = 100. Last update of data in use: 22 nd September 2011.	HICP is an economic indicator constructed to measure the changes over time in the prices of consumer goods and services acquired, used or paid for by households. HICP is a comparable inflation indicator for the Euro-zone countries, the EU countries and European Economic Area countries. HICP is the official indicator for inflation of consumer prices in the Euro zone used for variety of purposes including monetary policy, instrument for assessment of the inflation processes in the member states according to the Maastricht criteria, etc. ²
Harmonised index of consumer prices – Food and non-alcoholic beverages - HICP-FNAB	HICP-FNAB is measured on monthly basis. Base – 2005 = 100. Last update of data in use: 22 nd September 2011.	HICP-FNAB is a specific HICP; it measures the changes over time in the consumer prices of food-products and non-alcoholic beverages.
Unemployment Rate (UR)	UR is measured on monthly basis. Last update of data in use: 22 nd September 2011.	The unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the labour force (seasonally adjusted). The labour force is the total number of people employed and unemployed.

Europe's Energy Portal³

Variable	Variable details	Definition of variable
Unleaded A95 (A95)	Measured on monthly basis. Last update of data in use: 12 th October 2011.	Average retail price per litre of fuel A95, including all taxes.
Diesel (Diesel)	Measured on monthly basis. Last update of data in use: 12 th October 2011.	Average retail price per litre of fuel Diesel, including all taxes.

INTEGRO Association

Variable	Variable details	Definition of variable
All monitored media (AMM)	Measured on monthly basis.	The generated variable measures the number of Roma content articles per month in all monitored media.
Non-nationalistic liberal media (NLM)	Measured on monthly basis.	The generated variable measures the number of Roma content articles per month in the monitored non-nationalistic liberal media.
Nationalistic media (NM)	Measured on monthly basis.	The generated variable measures the number of Roma content articles per month in the monitored nationalistic media.

² More details about the Harmonised Indices of Consumer Prices can be found at http://circa.europa.eu/Public/irc/dsis/hiocp/library?l=/public/short_guide_users/en-shortguide-ks-be-04-0/_EN_1.0_&a=d

³ Europe's Energy Portal: <http://www.energy.eu/>

RESULTS

The statistical analysis was divided into two stages: preparatory and essential. The preparatory results (see the appendix) are calculations testing the possibility if the available time series data can be included in a correlation matrix. Calculating the correlation matrix was the essential stage of the conducted statistical analysis whose results are commented below.

Testing time series for autocorrelation

Autocorrelation most often arises when the data is ordered by time, e.g. the case we have at stake here. Autocorrelation can either inflate or deflate standard errors and make us think a relationship significant when it is actually not, or, instead, it hides a statistically significant relationship.

Because of the above considerations, during the preparatory stage of the statistical analysis, all variables were tested for autocorrelation using Box-Pierce portmanteau test for autocorrelation. The Q statistics (Box-Pierce portmanteau) tests series of null hypotheses that all autocorrelations up to and including each lag are zero (Hamilton; 2008: 375).

The data of the variables *unemployment rate* (UR), *unleaded A95* (A95), *all monitored media* (AMM) and *nationalistic media* (NM) turned out to be random and none of the autocorrelation coefficients statistically significant (see appendix). The autocorrelation coefficients for the rest of the variables, e.g. *harmonised index of consumer prices* (HICP) harmonised index of consumer prices – food and non-alcoholic beverages (HICP-FNAP) and *diesel* (Diesel), were also statistically insignificant showing minor deviations in the end lags.

P values being larger than 0.05 allowed me to reject the null hypotheses and generalise that no significant autocorrelations have been observed among the variables in use, e.g. *white noise* without any significant autocorrelation (respectively, there is no methodological obstacle to include them in the correlation matrix).

Correlation analysis of the data

All variables under discussion in this study are interval and thus Pearson Product Moment Correlation⁴ was used in the analysis. Results are presented in table 1.

INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

The statistically significant (asterixed) correlation coefficients (* see table 1) provide the answers of the above hypotheses in regard to the presence or absence of relationship between each two of the variables under discussion.

Prices and the volume of Roma articles in the media

During the monitoring period, we did not observe a statistically significant relationship between the overall inflation indicator (HICP) and the

⁴ For details see Agresti, A. and Finley, B. 1997. *Statistical Methods for the Social Sciences*. [3rd ed.], Prentice Hall. ISBN 0-13-526526-6 p.318-321

Table 1

Correlation matrix of the variables for movement of prices, unemployment and number of Roma articles published in media

	HICP	HICP-FNAB	UR	A95	Diesel	AMM	NLM	NM
HICP	—————							
HICP-FNAB	0.94**	—————						
UR	0.68	0.83*	—————					
A95	0.90**	0.72	0.38	—————				
Diesel	0.86*	0.89**	0.91**	0.66	—————			
AMM	-0.66	-0.76*	-0.87*	-0.32	-0.87*	—————		
NLM	-0.69	-0.78*	-0.87*	-0.35	-0.88**	0.99**	—————	
NM	0.38	0.30	-0.17	0.44	-0.01	0.19	0.13	—————
N=7	* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and *** p<0.001							

activeness of media in publishing Roma content articles. Further, such a relationship was not observed either when the monitored media were regrouped according their value orientation. HICP's methodology is one of the possible explanations for this result: many of the components of the HICP are definitely not among the readers' burning questions of the day (readers rarely/never purchase on daily basis electronic goods, cars, tourist services and the like). In other words, the inflation of certain goods which inevitably affect the value of HICP might be of importance to editorial boards but we cannot argue the same about the inflation of a great number of goods and services (which the HICP is constructed to measure).

Foods, non-alcoholic drinks and fuels became those goods whose prices, for reason, focused the research interest of this study: these are the type of prices which the vast majority of people happen to deal with on daily basis. There are justified grounds to presume that publishers and editorial boards of daily newspapers consider these prices an important topic. Without going into further details here, it is necessary to note that the above mentioned products are being sold in supermarkets and petrol stations on daily basis just like the dailies. A great deal of newspaper (news portal) readers goes to supermarkets, shops and petrol stations almost every single day. Choosing this analytical approach towards the relationship between a food and beverage inflation indicator and the number of Roma content articles led to completely different results.

The relationship between the variables HICP-FNAB and AMM appears to be quite strong ($R=-0.76$). The coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.56$) shows that a change in the prices of foods and non-alcoholic drinks is somehow related to approximately 56% of the change in the number of Roma articles published in all monitored

media. The type of association discussed here (e.g. the correlation measured with the respective analytical statistical tool) is such that I am not in a position to argue how, e.g. directly or indirectly (through an/other variable/s), the food and drink prices affect the structure of media content in terms of Roma articles. **The last sentence refers to all relationships (associations) discussed in this study.**

Furthermore, it is necessary to note that the relationship between the variables HICP-FNAB and AMM is inversely proportional, e.g. the increase in prices of food products and non-alcoholic beverages takes place along with an overall reduction of the number of Roma articles in all media.

The correlation coefficient between HICP-FNAB and NLM (the number of Roma articles in all non-nationalistic liberal media) is also negative $R=-0.78$; R^2 is approximately equal to 0.61. By analogy with the above said, it can be concluded that the media content of newspapers like *Dnevnik*, *Klassa*, etc. (which were defined as liberal and non-nationalistic) is strongly affected by changes in prices of food products and non-alcoholic beverages. In other words, these are empirical grounds to argue that (not only in theory but also in practice) a liberal ideology would show more interest in and pay stronger attention to economic processes than ethnicity issues.

I cannot argue the same when it comes to the monitored nationalistic newspaper *Ataka* (the NM variable). The correlation coefficient between NM and HICP-FNAB is positive $R=0.3$, e.g. proportional relationship; e.g. 2.53 times lower than the correlation coefficient of HICP-FNAB and AMM variables. But most importantly: this coefficient is not statistically significant. To put it differently, **the number of Roma articles in a nationalistic medium does not depend (in terms of correlation) on the movement of prices of foods and non-alcoholic drinks.** This provides grounds to presume that independently from the intensity of important economic processes, the latter have no significant bearing on the volume of Roma content in the nationalistic type of media.

Fuel prices and the volume of Roma content the media

I would not like to avoid one of the most important issues concerning millions of Bulgarian car owners. Petrol and diesel prices are burning questions which, in 2011, made more than hundred thousand people took to the street and protest all over Bulgaria. All media paid due attention to these protests. Of course, media cover the fuel topics not only in times of protests. It makes sense and probably pays off well if a medium implements information strategy serving the interests of more than one hundred thousand lorry drivers whose businesses directly or indirectly depend on the price of diesel and the millions of car drivers who closely follow petrol and diesel prices.

Within the framework of such a context, the correlation analysis offers quite interesting results. Taking into consideration the press as a whole and the non-nationalistic liberal media (which dominate the media market in Bulgaria), we can hardly remain unnoticed the very strong relationship between diesel prices and the volume of published Roma content (see again table 1). The AMM variable and the price of diesel strongly correlate: $R=-0.87$ and R^2 approximately equal to 0.76. The correlation between the NLM and the Diesel variables is as follows: $R=-0.88$ and R^2 approximately equal to 0.77. The relationship is inversely proportional just like the relationship between the inflation indicator for foods and non-alcoholic drinks.

In other words, when diesel price goes up, it makes no sense for us to expect more Roma content in the media, and especially in the non-nationalistic liberal media. This conclusion though is not valid for nationalistic media: the number of Roma articles in the monitored *Ataka* newspaper was by no means affected by the change in price of diesel. The correlation coefficient between the NM and Diesel variables is close to zero ($R=-0.01$) and is not statistically significant, e.g. again ideological principles seem to be the guiding light when editorial boards structure the content of nationalistic media.

The other fuel in our analysis (unleaded A95) shows similar to the HICP variable type of relationship with the volume of Roma content in the different media. There are no statistically significant correlation coefficients between each pair of the variables A95, AMM, NLM and NM. It is possible that the ratio between petrol cars (which cannot run on methane or LPG) and diesel cars (having passed the obligatory technical checks) could be strongly in favour of the diesel cars; such a ratio can respectively neutralise the importance of the unleaded A95 price fluctuations. In Bulgaria, there is almost no alternative for the heavy duty trucks to run on gas or methane. Unfortunately, there are no transport data that could allow us testing the above attempts for explanation.

Unemployment rate and the volume of Roma content in the media

Before I continue my comments about the volume of Roma content in the media from the standpoint of employment, I would like to elaborate on two correlation coefficients. There is an extremely strong (statistically significant) relationship between the price of diesel and the unemployment rate ($R=0.91$, $p<0.01$). The strength of the correlation association between the Diesel and UR variables turned out higher than I expected. Thus, it is obligatory to note that the increase of the price of diesel goes hand in hand with an increase of the unemployment rate in Bulgaria: during monitoring period each EUR 0.20 (approx. BGN 0.39) increase in the price of diesel coincided with an increase of the unemployment rate by approximately 0.18 percentage points. The correlation analysis of the A95 and UR variables provided no grounds to argue about an existing significant relationship between these variables.

The correlation coefficient between the UR and AMM variables is $R=-0.87$ and statistically significant at the 0.05 level; the correlation coefficient between the UR and NLM is the same (see table 1). It can be inferred that the number of Roma articles in the media and in the non-nationalistic liberal media in particular has something to do with the unemployment rate in Bulgaria. As already found above, the content structure of the nationalistic medium has not been affected in terms of Roma articles by unemployment.

The correlation matrix produces statistically analysed results for each possible pair of variables included in a model, e.g. so to say an isolated relationship between a pair of variables. The matrix does not provide any information on how all variables in the model interact together as a whole. The above analysis shows three very strong relationships concerning the volume of the Roma content in the media. However, it should be noted that the strength (represented through the correlation coefficients) of these relationships is additionally heightened because of the specifics of the correlation analysis method. Each of the variables representing the price of foods and non-

alcoholic drinks, the price of diesel and unemployment adds tenths to the value of its coefficient when it is not analysed in a complex model including all variables acting together. A close look at table 1 (see, for example, how variable Diesel correlates with the variables UR, HICP and HICP-FNAB) confirms this specificity of the model: the correlation coefficients between these variables are high and statistically significant.

Given the above results and considerations, I have grounds for at least two conclusions. This study can become a point of departure for a more analytical modelling of the process of structuring of the ethnic content in the media under the influence of macroeconomic processes. There is plenty of evidence to answer our research question: yes, certain macroeconomic processes affect the structure of the content in the media, especially in terms of ethnic content.

CONCLUSION

This study provides grounds for some major conclusions. In the first place, the general conclusion is that we have serious grounds to argue that the structure of content (e.g. the presence or absence of articles about the Roma) in the Bulgarian press is affected by some microeconomic processes like the movement of prices and employment. The specificity here is that if the value orientation of a medium is nationalistic, the influence of the macroeconomic processes is strongly reduced and improbable.

When the prices of food products and diesel increase, or the proportion of unemployed people rises, the non-nationalistic liberal daily newspapers (tend to) strongly diminish the number of articles they publish about the Roma and Roma problems.

The Roma issues can be part of the content of a particular medium for different reasons; on one hand, they can be the burning question of the day, and on the other, a topic which is covered on daily basis regardless of presence or absence of actual news concerning the Roma. The latter is usually inspired by different interests although the common sense is unlikely to presume good intentions (of course, I am sure there are many exceptions) when important news and events are ignored while unnecessary emphasis is put on the Roma issues.

Because of the type of the association between the number of Roma articles and the microeconomic processes, the influence of the latter on the former seems obvious. If we hypothetically imagine that editorial boards decide to massively publish Roma articles, I argue that employment conditions will not improve, neither will prices decrease; only the statistically significant relationships among the variables will be lost, e.g. all media will be likely to resemble the *Ataka* newspaper in terms of content. It is possible, though, that via reasonable economic, financial and social policies, the macroeconomic indicators of prices and unemployment can be put under control and their up and down movements be minimised to insignificant fluctuations; although, this seems a very unlikely scenario it is a possible one. If it happens for a continuous period of time, the predominantly economic news content will provoke interest among fewer readers; the majority of the reading public will be looking for different type of news and topical issues. On their part, the editorial boards will have to change the content of their daily newspapers, respectively the profile their

journalists and reporters in terms of knowledge, competencies and interpretative and analytical skills. Each change of structure and content of a medium is either a market share change or a change in society (or at least among its reading part) and people's attitudes (or both).

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APPENDIX

Table 1

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the HICP variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.60	3.81
2	0.20	4.30
3	-0.21	4.97
4	-0.42	8.66
5	-0.40	13.69*
6	-0.27	18.40**
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 2

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the HICP-FNAB variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.46	2.20
2	0.15	2.48
3	-0.09	2.60
4	-0.26	4.04
5	-0.37	8.34
6	-0.39	17.74**
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 3

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the UR variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.50	2.59
2	-0.01	2.59
3	-0.32	4.18
4	-0.33	6.53
5	-0.23	8.21
6	-0.11	8.92
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 4

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the A95 variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.55	3.20
2	0.04	3.21
3	-0.36	5.26
4	-0.40	8.69
5	-0.19	9.87
6	-0.13	10.94
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 5

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the Diesel variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.60	3.79
2	0.10	3.91
3	-0.21	4.59
4	-0.44	8.71
5	-0.40	13.74*
6	-0.15	15.13*
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 6

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the AMM variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.42	1.82
2	-0.12	1.99
3	-0.19	2.57
4	-0.25	3.88
5	-0.26	6.04
6	-0.10	6.61
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 7

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the NLM variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.42	1.88
2	-0.11	2.04
3	-0.16	2.42
4	-0.24	3.68
5	-0.30	6.45
6	-0.11	7.26
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		

Table 8

Box-Pierce portmanteau test results (Q statistic) for statistical significance of the autocorrelation coefficients of the NM variable

Lag	Autocorrelation coefficient	Q
1	0.06	0.33
2	-0.27	0.92
3	-0.31	2.44
4	-0.07	2.54
5	0.11	2.91
6	-0.02	2.93
* p<0.05, ** p<0.01 and ***p<0.001		